

TIME AND TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF THE VISCOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF PEEK/IM7

José Daniel D. Melo ^a, Donald W. Radford ^b

^a *Departamento de Engenharia Mecânica – Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte
Natal, RN 59072-970. BRAZIL daniel.melo@ufrnet.br*

^b *Composite Materials, Manufacture and Structures Laboratory
Colorado State University, Fort Collins, CO 80523-1374*

SUMMARY: Understanding viscoelastic properties of composite materials is essential for the design and analysis of many advanced structures. However, experimental viscoelastic characterization of anisotropic materials can be complicated because of the number of independent parameters to be evaluated. Recently, an approach leading to the 3-D viscoelastic characterization of transversely isotropic materials using a reduced number of measured parameters has been developed. The model reduces the number of independent parameters to describe the viscoelastic behavior of transversely isotropic materials, which greatly simplifies the experimental procedures. Based on this recently developed model, the present work evaluates time and temperature effects on the viscoelastic properties of a fiber reinforced lamina. The experimental investigation is conducted on sub-scale specimens loaded in flexure, using Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) equipment. Ultimately, the approach presented in this work will allow the construction of master curves for the independent viscoelastic parameters that characterize a transversely isotropic material. Therefore, the experimental technique presented in this work provides a means for the study of viscoelastic properties of fiber reinforced composites, and constitutes a valuable contribution to the understanding of time and temperature dependence of these mechanical properties.

KEYWORDS: Viscoelasticity, Dynamic Mechanical Analysis, PEEK, Transversely isotropic.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials demonstrating “designed damping” are becoming of ever-greater interest to the engineering community. With modern computer tools it seems possible to predict the effects of lamination sequence, ply orientation and constituent material properties on the damping performance of composites. Unfortunately, the ability to generate numerical predictions that match the damping observed in practice is limited by the reliability of the available viscoelastic material properties data. Obtaining accurate viscoelastic properties information over wide temperature ranges and long times is even more difficult. Thus, much of the modeling of “designed damping” to-date has been performed using assumed viscoelastic properties data, or at best data from a very limited range of conditions.

A well-accepted concept in polymer behavior is the equivalence between temperature and frequency. A particular temperature transition determined by Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) measurements, at a given applied frequency, can be observed at a lower temperature if the applied vibration frequency is decreased. In this sense, temperature and frequency produce opposite effects on the property considered and a reduction in temperature can be compensated by a reduction in the frequency of measurement. Thus, according to this equivalence, the effect of reducing the applied frequency is similar to that of increasing the temperature.

Based on the equivalence between temperature and frequency (time), Time-Temperature Superposition has been used, for many years, as a way to investigate long-term behavior of materials through extrapolation of a series of short-time tests. Normally, properties are evaluated at several temperatures and within a given frequency range and, because of the equivalent effect of time (of frequency) and temperature, the data can be superposed by shifting individual curves about a given reference temperature, generating a master curve. After shifting the data, the master curve produced covers a range much greater than each individual collected data. Master curves are generated for storage modulus and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) [1]. These master curves provide essential information on material behavior, for each of the viscoelastic parameters, and enable prediction of the parameters outside of the available measurement range of the equipment.

This technique can be very advantageous in the prediction of the material behavior at low frequencies, eliminating the need to perform time-consuming low frequency tests. The approach has been shown to be capable of predicting long-term changes in strength and modulus, and has been suggested as a potential prediction method for the fatigue strength of fiber-reinforced plastics [2,3]. In addition, modern Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) equipment has evolved to the point that it can be programmed to automatically perform a series of frequency scans at different temperatures. Finally, the modern DMA equipment incorporates software offering built-in functions to automate the generation of time-temperature master curves, based on the measured data

A DMA-based approach was recently developed to investigate viscoelastic properties of fiber-reinforced composites [4]. A mechanics model was developed, which describes the 3-D viscoelastic properties of a transversely isotropic material, based on five independent storage moduli and three damping loss factors ($\tan \delta$). Also, it has been determined, that, for the case of a transversely isotropic lamina, the computation of all 3-D viscoelastic properties can be accomplished from three bending tests, providing that two Poisson's ratios, ν_{12} and ν_{23} , are known from elastic measurements. This approach has been successfully applied in the viscoelastic characterization of PEEK/IM7 unidirectional tape [4].

The DMA-based approach offers great potential to investigate temperature and frequency effects on viscoelastic properties of composites, since the viscoelastic parameters are experimentally evaluated in a global sense, instead of being predicted by micromechanics. Moreover, if these properties can be evaluated at several temperatures and within a given frequency range, the data can be superposed to generate master curves for the properties studied. To assess this ability, this study uses DMA measured parameters in unidirectional sub-scale bend beam specimens, to determine the viscoelastic material properties for a transversely isotropic, fiber reinforced material, over ranges of temperature and frequency. Time and temperature dependence of the viscoelastic properties of transversely isotropic PEEK/IM7 laminae are determined from DMA measurements in unidirectional beams with three different fiber orientations. The results over temperature and frequency ranges are compared for consistency and, thus, the potential of the method to generate time-temperature master curves is evaluated.

REDUCED PARAMETER VISCOELASTIC MODEL [4]

The general form of the linear theory of a viscoelastic body is given by [5]

$$\sigma_{ij}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t C_{ijkl}(t-\tau) d\varepsilon_{kl}(\tau) \quad (1)$$

The moduli for a viscoelastic material are complex, with real and imaginary components:

$$C_{ijkl}^* = C'_{ijkl} + iC''_{ijkl} \quad (2)$$

Where: C_{ijkl}^* are the complex moduli, C'_{ijkl} are the storage moduli and C''_{ijkl} are the loss moduli.

Poisson's ratios are described as time-dependent functions according to fundamental viscoelastic theory [6,7,8,9,10,11]. However, experimental measurements of Poisson's ratios of fiber-reinforced composites, under structural conditions, have indicated that, for these materials, Poisson's ratios do not vary significantly with loading frequency [12]. Thus, the assumption of time-independent Poisson's ratios has been used, by many authors, to simplify the characterization of glass and carbon fiber-reinforced composites, under structural loading conditions. Writing the complex moduli in matrix form, the assumption of time-independent Poisson's ratios implies that the off-diagonal terms of $[C'']$ do not exhibit independent viscoelastic behavior. Thus, the complex moduli can be written in matrix form as,

$$[C^*] = [C'] + i[C''] \quad (3)$$

Then, if symmetry conditions of $[C'']$ are considered, only three damping coefficients, *i.e.*, η_1 , η_2 , and η_6 are independent. Thus, the matrix $[C'']$ can be expressed in contracted form as [4]

$$[C''] = \begin{bmatrix} C'_{11} & C'_{12} & C'_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C'_{12} & C'_{22} & C'_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C'_{12} & C'_{23} & C'_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C'_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C'_{66} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C'_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \eta_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \eta_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \eta_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \eta_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \eta_6 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \eta_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, according to the mathematical model described in equations (3) and (4), the viscoelastic constitutive relationships of transversely isotropic materials can be described based on eight parameters: five independent dynamic stiffness parameters, E'_1 , E'_2 , G'_{12} , $\nu'_{12}=\nu_{12}$, and $\nu'_{23}=\nu_{23}$, plus three independent damping loss factors, η_1 , η_2 , and η_6 .

MATERIALS AND TEST SPECIMENS

The material tested was APC-2/IM7, unidirectional prepreg tape, manufactured by Cytec Engineered Materials Inc., with a resin content of 32% and a fiber areal weight of 145g/m². An 8 ply unidirectional $[(0)_8]_T$, 150.0 x 200.0 mm laminate, was produced in a hot-press, at a temperature of 395°C for 45 minutes, and under an applied pressure of 690 kPa (100 psi). Beam specimens were cut from the processed laminates using a diamond abrasive saw. Unidirectional laminated beams were cut from the $[(0)_8]_T$ plate with fibers oriented at 0°, 30°, and 90°, with respect to the beam length. In this research, the properties of these unidirectional specimens are assumed to be a true representation of the properties of one unidirectional layer. Therefore, the measured properties of these unidirectional specimens are referred to as lamina properties. Careful control of ply orientation was undertaken during the cutting process.

Figure 1 - Bend-beam specimens.

After the cutting procedure, the specimen edges were sanded flat for better dimensional precision. Finally, the specimens were conditioned to reduce effects of residual stresses and moisture introduced during specimen preparation. Accurate dimensions of each specimen were measured using a hand-held micrometer. The specimen dimensions were nominally 50.0 x 4.0 x 1.0 mm (Figure 1).

EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

The model presented in equations 3 and 4, to determine the viscoelastic properties of transversely isotropic laminae, assumes that the Poisson's ratios, ν_{12} and ν_{23} , are known and that they include only the real (not imaginary) part. Therefore, these elastic properties need to first be determined. After the determination of the two Poisson's ratios for the material studied, over the temperature range of interest, dynamic flexural measurements in beams are carried out to complete the viscoelastic characterization. Two types of dynamic measurements were conducted: temperature scan and frequency scan. The temperature scan measurements were performed over the temperature range of -20°C to +120°C, with a heating rate of 3.0°C/min, and under a constant frequency of 1.0 Hz. The actual temperature sweep test was performed over a greater range - from -25°C to +125°C - to ensure that the rate of change of temperature was steady over the temperature range of -20°C to +120°C. The frequency scans were conducted at room temperature and over a frequency range from 0.1 Hz to 10 Hz, with an exponential frequency change rate using 10 data points per decade.

Sub-scale dynamic measurements were carried out using a Rheometric Scientific DMTA-V, in a 3-point bending testing mode, with a 40.0mm span between the supports. Three-point bending was selected as the preferred testing geometry since clamped boundaries are reported to affect the damping measurements, increasing the measured damping [13]. Moreover, for the tests carried out over a range of temperatures, in-plane forces, due to the mismatch in coefficients of thermal expansion between the beam specimen and the material of the supports, are not introduced since the beam is free to expand at the supports.

All dynamic tests were carried out under a sinusoidal strain-controlled mode. A very small strain amplitude (0.01%) is used throughout the measurements since the model applied, for viscoelastic material characterization, assumes that the specific damping capacity is independent of the amplitude of strain, which is a valid assumption only for very small strains. The beam specimens were pre-stressed with an applied force 10% larger than the force necessary to produce the desired strain amplitude. This procedure guarantees that the center probe is always in contact with the beam. The force necessary to pre-stress the beam is automatically calculated, through a series of static tests, by the computer control of the DMTA-V and corrected, if necessary, throughout the experimental procedure.

Dynamic tests in beams with three different fiber orientations are necessary for the viscoelastic characterization [4]. Sub-scale flexure tests in unidirectional beams with fibers oriented at 0°, 30°, and 90°, with respect to the beam length, were conducted. Other off-axis angles were not considered in this research due to easy of manufacture of the 30° off-axis specimens, which may ultimately help reduce the errors related to ply misalignment. The storage moduli, E'_1 and E'_2 , and the damping loss factors, η_1 and η_2 , are measured directly from oscillatory bend-beam tests of unidirectional laminae with fibers oriented at 0° and at 90°, with respect to the beam length. Then, the storage shear modulus, G'_{12} , and the damping constant, η_6 , are computed based on the measured storage moduli, E'_1 , E'_2 , and damping loss factors, η_1 , η_2 , the properties E'_{xx} and η_x , measured from the bending test performed in the off-axis unidirectional beam specimen (30°), and the measured value of the Poisson's ratio, ν_{12} . The equations applied in the computation of the storage shear modulus, G'_{12} , and the damping constant, η_6 , are [4]:

$$\eta_x = \frac{\Delta W}{2\pi W} = \frac{1}{\bar{S}'_{11}} \left\{ \frac{\eta_1}{E'_1} \cos^4(\theta) + \frac{\eta_2}{E'_2} \sin^4(\theta) + \left[\frac{\eta_6}{G'_{12}} - (\eta_1 + \eta_2) \frac{\nu_{12}}{E'_1} \right] \sin^2(\theta) \cos^2(\theta) \right\} \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{S}'_{11} = S'_{11} \cos^4(\theta) + S'_{22} \sin^4(\theta) + (2S'_{12} + S'_{66}) \cos^2(\theta) \sin^2(\theta) \quad (6)$$

Therefore, using the procedure described, the viscoelastic properties of the material studied are investigated over ranges of temperature and frequency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Elastic Properties: The 3-D elastic properties for PEEK/IM7 were determined, over the range of temperature of -20°C to +120°C, according to a proposed approach, making use of coefficients of thermal expansion measurements [14]. The elastic properties for intervals of 20°C and over the entire temperature range studied are presented in Table 1. The data in Table 1 show that the longitudinal elastic modulus, E_1 , does not show any change with temperature. This behavior was expected, considering that E_1 is mainly controlled by the fiber properties, which are insensitive to temperature changes within the temperature range studied. The two Poisson's ratios, ν_{12} and ν_{23} , show a small increase with temperature. A decrease in the transverse modulus E_2 and shear modulus, G_{12} , is observed with increasing temperature. These two parameters are noticeably affected by the matrix properties.

Table 1 - Elastic properties of PEEK/IM7 related to temperature

Temp. (°C)	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{23}
-20	164.84	10.16	7.42	0.34	0.48
0	164.84	10.10	7.16	0.34	0.49
20	164.84	9.98	6.92	0.34	0.49
40	164.84	9.84	6.71	0.34	0.49
60	164.84	9.75	6.51	0.35	0.49
80	164.84	9.63	6.33	0.35	0.50
100	164.84	9.29	6.16	0.35	0.50
120	164.84	8.30	6.00	0.35	0.50

Temperature Dependence of the Viscoelastic Properties: The measured storage modulus and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) data, corresponding to two beam tests in each of the three different fiber orientations tested, were averaged for the calculation of the material viscoelastic properties. For the calculation of the averages, in each fiber orientation, a sixth degree polynomial was used to fit the loss factor data, while for the storage modulus a linear fit was applied. There is no fundamental reason in the selection of the order of fit used other than the fact that they were found to provide the best representation of the raw data collected. A high degree polynomial was applied for the curve that describes the temperature dependence of the loss factor, to allow contouring the irregular shape with peaks, which are a characteristic of these curves. Essentially, the polynomial fitting was used as a curve smoothing technique, and also as a way to generate equations of the relationships for follow-up manipulation. The average of the storage modulus and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) data, from two specimens tested in each fiber orientation, are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Average storage moduli and loss factors for unidirectional beams.

The temperature-sweep tests for all unidirectional beams (Figure 2) show an increase in $\tan \delta$ and decrease in dynamic modulus with increasing temperature. However the temperature influence was different between unidirectional beam specimens with different fiber orientation, as expected. Over the temperature range studied, the carbon fiber properties are expected to show little, or no, temperature relation. In contrast, the viscoelastic properties of the PEEK thermoplastic matrix are more temperature-dependent. Therefore, the temperature effect in specimens, where the properties are more fiber-dominated, such as beams with 0° fiber orientation, the temperature effect is reduced.

Using the average of the measured viscoelastic properties, and the Poisson's ratios, ν_{12} and ν_{23} , previously determined over the same temperature range, the viscoelastic properties of PEEK/IM7 were determined over the temperature range of -20°C to $+120^\circ\text{C}$. The temperature dependence of the

eight independent parameters that completely characterize the material is presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3 - Variation of storage moduli and Poisson's ratios with temperature for PEEK/IM7.

Figure 4 - Variation of loss factors with temperature for PEEK/IM7.

The modulus of the carbon fiber is very large compared to the polymeric matrix. Therefore, since the temperature effect on the carbon fiber properties is negligible, within the temperature range studied, the changes in modulus with temperature are dependent on the fiber direction. However, even in the fiber-dominated modulus, E'_1 , there was a trend indicating decrease with temperature (Figure 3). The small change observed in E'_1 suggests changes not only in matrix properties but also changes in the fiber-matrix interface. Changes in matrix properties alone could not account for the total change in modulus, especially because the maximum temperature is considerably below the glass transition temperature. The changes in the other two modulus components, where the matrix properties are significant, such as E'_2 and G'_{12} , are larger due to the changes in matrix properties with temperature, combined with changes at the interface.

Contrary to the response of the modulus, the damping properties of the polymeric matrix are significantly higher compared to the carbon fiber damping. Therefore, most of the composite damping is a result of the matrix damping and the fiber-matrix interface response. Changes in damping with temperature were much larger than changes in dynamic modulus (Figure 4). Even in the fiber direction where the changes in modulus are very small, considerable changes in damping were detected, over the temperature range.

Frequency Dependence of the Viscoelastic Properties: The measurement of viscoelastic properties over a frequency range allows the determination of the material response to various shear rates. In this study, frequency effects in viscoelastic properties of PEEK/IM7 unidirectional beams with different fiber orientations were investigated by sweeping the frequency across a frequency range of two decades, from 0.1 Hz to 10 Hz, at a constant temperature of approximately 20°C (room temperature).

As in the temperature sweep tests, two specimens were tested in each fiber orientation. In order to calculate the averages of measured storage modulus and loss factor data for each fiber orientation, a linear fit was applied to the raw storage modulus data, while for the loss factors, a logarithmic fit was used to properly represent the measured frequency dependency. The average storage modulus and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) data for all fiber orientations tested are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Frequency dependence of storage moduli and loss factors for unidirectional beams.

The average of the measured viscoelastic properties for the beam specimens with fiber orientations of 0°, 30°, and 90°, and the Poisson's ratios, ν_{12} and ν_{23} , previously determined in the elastic characterization, at the temperature of 20°C, were used for the determination of the viscoelastic properties of PEEK/IM7 at different frequencies. The frequency dependence of the independent parameters that completely characterize the material is presented in Figure 6. The two Poisson's ratios, ν_{12} and ν_{23} , are not included since they assumed frequency independent.

According to the data presented in Figure 6, the storage moduli E'_1 , E'_2 and G'_{12} , were practically independent of frequency over the range studied. However, changes in damping with frequency were considerable. Even in the fiber direction (1-axis) where the changes in modulus are very small, considerable changes in damping were detected, over the frequency range. Figure 6 shows that the lines of frequency dependence of the three damping loss factors, η_1 , η_2 , and η_6 , are roughly parallel to each other. Nevertheless, the limited data used in this research is not enough for a conclusive statement regarding this observation.

Figure 6 - Variation of Storage moduli and loss factors with frequency for PEEK/IM7.

In general, at low frequencies polymeric materials flow more, acting in a similar fashion to flow at elevated temperature, thus showing a larger damping. As the frequency increases, the material behaves more elastically. Therefore, both storage modulus and loss factor vary with frequency. As mentioned in previous sections, the damping of carbon fiber reinforced polymeric composites is derived mainly from the matrix and the fiber/matrix interface response. The decrease in $\tan \delta$ of the composite material with frequency is related to restrictions of chain motions of the polymer at higher frequencies. The same effect is also responsible for an increase in storage modulus. The results show that the damping, $\tan \delta$, is considerably more sensitive to changes in frequency than the storage modulus.

The frequency dependency may be more considerable, at temperatures near the region of a transition such as the T_g , because of the temperature-frequency equivalence. For the composite material evaluated herein, the glass transition temperature of the polymeric matrix determined by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) is in the region of 150°C, and the frequency sweep tests were conducted at room temperature (approximately 20°C). In general, an increase in frequency will increase the temperature at which the transition occurs as less time is available for molecular rearrangement. Therefore, the frequency dependency of the viscoelastic properties is even more critical if the usage temperature is near the range where a thermal transition occurs.

Comparison Between Temperature and Frequency Sweep Tests Data: In this investigation, the frequency sweep measurements were performed at a temperature of approximately 20°C, and all the temperature sweep tests were conducted at a frequency of 1.0Hz. Therefore, the properties obtained from the frequency sweep tests at 1.0Hz, and those from temperature sweep tests at 20°C, should be similar, if the approach is valid. The direct comparison between these two sets of data is presented in Table 2. The table shows a good agreement for the three storage moduli, E'_1 , E'_2 , and G'_{12} obtained from the two types of measurements. However, all damping loss factors ($\tan \delta$) determined from frequency sweep tests were larger than those from temperature sweep tests.

Table 2 - Properties of PEEK/IM7 determined from temperature and frequency sweep tests.

Property	Freq. sweep	Temp. sweep	Difference
E'_1 (GPa)	151.5	154.9	2%
E'_2 (GPa)	9.3	10.0	7%
G'_{12} (GPa)	7.7	7.2	6%
η_1 (10^{-3})	5.4	5.1	6%
η_2 (10^{-3})	8.3	7.2	13%
η_6 (10^{-3})	11.6	10.6	8%

The smaller damping factors determined from the temperature sweep tests might be related to the rate of temperature increase used on these tests. All temperature sweep tests started at very low temperatures (-25°C) and the temperature was then increased at a constant rate of 3°C/min to the final temperature of 125°C. This procedure allowed data to be collected over the temperature range of -20°C to 120°C. The low damping loss factors obtained in these temperature tests may be an indication that the heating rate was too high and, at the time of the measurements, the specimen, or at least the internal layers of the specimen, was at a lower temperature than the equipment chamber, where the temperature is measured. The lower temperature of the specimens would explain the lower loss factors measured. The damping properties obtained at 40°C agree well with frequency sweep data, thus supporting this suggestion. Further, the largest difference between the two tests, 13%, was observed in the damping factor η_2 . In this case, in addition to the possibility of temperature gradient between the specimen and equipment chamber, Figure 4 shows a non-expected drop in the damping factor η_2 , at 20°C, which may be an indication of inaccurate measured data at this temperature. Temperature sweep tests at a lower heating rate would confirm the suggestion of a thermal lag in the measured data. If this is verified, then a temperature shift would need to be applied to the data presented.

FUTURE WORK

In this investigation, temperature and frequency effects on the viscoelastic properties of a unidirectional PEEK/IM7 prepreg lamina have been studied separately, using Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) equipment. The agreement of the data obtained from the two approaches – frequency scan and temperature scan - indicates that the DMA-based approach produces consistent data and does offer the potential for time-temperature studies of fiber reinforced composites. An experimental program to generate master curves for the viscoelastic properties of the material studied, using the DMA approach described, is planned. The main idea is to generate master curves for all independent storage moduli and loss factors that characterize the fiber reinforced material. The Poisson's ratios will be considered time-independent, as required by the model. DMA measurements in three unidirectional beams, at several temperatures and within a given frequency range, are planned. Initially, the same temperature and frequency ranges already used in this study will be considered. Based on the measured properties at each temperature, each independent viscoelastic parameter of the material will be determined, as related to frequency. Then, the data, for each parameter, will be superposed by shifting individual curves about a given reference temperature, thus, generating master curves for all viscoelastic parameters. Finally, the same procedure needs also to be applied in other materials with transverse isotropy for verification.

CONCLUSIONS

In this investigation, the 3-D viscoelastic properties of a transversely isotropic unidirectional lamina have been studied over ranges of frequency and temperature, separately. The study is based on a recently developed mechanics model, which requires a reduced number of independent parameters to be measured. An experimental procedure, which involves only three dynamic flexural tests, is used to determine viscoelastic properties of PEEK/IM7. Experiments were conducted in unidirectional beams, with three different fiber orientations, using the 3-point bend test mode. The procedure uses a standard piece of laboratory equipment (DMA), which allows the determination of the dynamic material properties over a range of temperatures and frequencies. The investigation evaluated changes in properties as related to temperature and frequency.

It was demonstrated in this work that frequency and temperature dependence of the viscoelastic properties of transversely isotropic laminae can be studied through DMA measurements in unidirectional beams, providing that the temperature dependence of the Poisson's ratios, ν_{12} and ν_{23} , is known. Using the approach discussed in this investigation, and performing frequency scans at different temperatures, master curves can be generated for the independent viscoelastic properties. These master curves will provide essential information of material behavior, for each of the viscoelastic parameters, outside of the available measuring range of the equipment. Ultimately, the ability to experimentally determine accurate viscoelastic parameters for composite laminae, over a

wide range of temperature and time, will enable accurate computer development of laminates with “designed damping”.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

CAPES – Brasília/Brazil is acknowledged for the fellowship support of the author José Daniel D. Melo during the development of this work. The authors are grateful to David Leach of Cytec Engineered Materials Inc. for donating the PEEK/IM7 prepreg used in this investigation. The authors are also indebted to Dr. John Suwardie of Rheometric Scientific Inc., who carried out the DMA experiments reported.

REFERENCES

1. Hunt, B. J., James, M. I., *Polymer Characterisation*, New York, NY, Blackie Academic & Professional, 1993.
2. Nakada, M., et al, “Time and Temperature Dependence of Flexural Fatigue Strength for Pitch-based CFRP,” *Proceedings of ICCM-12*, Paris, 1999.
3. Nakada, M., et al, “Time and Temperature Dependence of Static, Creep, and Fatigue Behavior for CF/Epoxy Strands,” *Proceedings of ICCM-12*, Paris, 1999.
4. Melo, J. D. D, and Radford, D. W., “Viscoelastic Characterization of Transversely Isotropic Composite Laminae,” *Journal of Composite Materials*, In Press.
5. Zinoviev, P. A., and Ermakov, Y. N. *Energy Dissipation in Composite Materials*. Lancaster, PA. Technomic Publishing Co., Inc., 1994.
6. Christensen, R. M. *Theory of Viscoelasticity – An Introduction*. New York, NY: Academic Press, 1981.
7. Drozdov, A. *Viscoelastic Structures – Mechanics of Growth and Aging*. New York, NY: Academic Press, 1998.
8. Drozdov, A. *Mechanics of Viscoelastic Solids*. New York, NY: Wiley, 1998.
9. Nielsen, L. E., and Landel, R. F. *Mechanical Properties of Polymers and Composites*. New York, NY: Marcel Dekker., 1994.
10. Hilton, H. H. “Implications and Constraints of Time-Independent Poisson Ratios in Linear Isotropic and Anisotropic Viscoelasticity,” *J. of Elasticity*, **63**,221-251, 2001.
11. Hilton, H. H., and Yi, S. “The Significance of (An)Isotropic Viscoelastic Poisson Ratio Stress and Time Dependencies,” *Int. J. Solids and Structures*, **35**,3081-3095, 1998.
12. Mead, D. J., and Joannides, R. J. “Measurement of the Dynamic Moduli and Poisson’s Ratios of a Transversely Isotropic Fibre-Reinforced Plastic,” *Composites*, **22**(1),15-29, 1991.
13. Hwang, S. J., Gibson, R. F., and Singh, J., “Decomposition of Coupling Effects on Damping of Laminated Composites Under Flexural Vibration,” *Composites Science and Technology*, **43**,159-169, 1992.
14. Melo, J. D. D., and Radford, D. W., “Elastic Properties of PEEK/IM7 Related to Temperature”, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, In Press.

BIOGRAPHIES

José Daniel Diniz Melo is a Professor of Mechanical Engineering at the Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil. He received his Ph.D in Mechanical Engineering at Colorado State University and his Masters of Science degree in Mechanical Engineering at the University of Maine. He obtained his Bachelors degrees in Mechanical Engineering and also in Civil Engineering, at the Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil. Professor Melo’s research interests are mainly focused on mechanical properties of composite materials.

Donald W. Radford is an Associate Professor of Mechanical Engineering at Colorado State University. He is the Director of the Composite Materials, Manufacture, and Structures Laboratory. He received his Ph.D. in Materials Engineering at Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, his MASc. in Metallurgical Engineering and BASc. in Mechanical Engineering at the University of British Columbia. Professor Radford has been involved in research in the field of advanced composite materials for over 20 years. His research interests primarily focus on processing effects and process induced distortion.